

Scheduling in Distributed Systems - Issues and Challenges

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Abstract:

Distributed Computing System is a computational setup with several autonomous systems connected each other and working together, on a common application. Each of the systems having their own Processors, Memory, Storage and Clock, a smooth coordination is essential in getting the task executed, using available local as well as remote resources. Getting High Performance Computation(HPC) over such Distributed Systems requires various techniques and mainly includes Distributed Scheduling. Basically methods like Local Scheduling, Proportional Sharing Scheduling and Predictive Scheduling. In Local Scheduling, a process will be assigned with only local available resource where as in Proportional Scheduling, a process will consume a portion of resource that depends on its relative shares allotted to it. In case of Predictive Scheduling, using the algorithm, resources can be assigned to a active process and this may keep changing dynamically. Performance of a Distributed Computing System can be enhanced further by using proper scheduling methods like these. This paper will discuss these three different scheduling approaches with its merits and demerits in Distributed Systems.

Keywords: Distributed Systems; High Performance Computation; Local Scheduling; Proportional Sharing Scheduling and Predictive Scheduling.

1.Introduction

Distributed Systems is one such computational environments having several autonomous systems connected each other by strong communication network and working together, on a common application. Distributed Systems provide better Reliability as well as Availability compared to traditional systems due to the existence of multiple resources both Hardware as well as Software. While designing a Distributed System, smart design strategies will contribute to improve the overall computational performance and hence can achieve HPC[2]. Few of the techniques to improve the performance are Distributed Database Design, Database Allocation and Migration of Database or Application within the Distributed System[2]. Apart

from the database design Distributed Scheduling also contributes towards the performance of such Distributed Systems.

2. Overview of the Scheduling

Job scheduling is composed of two inter-dependent steps like, Allocation of processes to nodes and scheduling of the processes over time. When a job is submitted to the system, a description of the attributes of the job is also submitted to the system to specify the resource requirement, such as expected CPU time, memory size requirement, etc. Latter job placement will be done, to decide which node to run the submitted job. At the same time, the system maintains an information table, either to record the current resource status of each workstation. Then, a matchmaking frame will do matching work to find the best suitable set of workstations to cater the need submitted job. Jobs will be decomposed into small processes, and then they will be distributed to those assigned workstations. The local scheduler on each of these individual workstation, allocates some time-slices to the process based on its policies so as to achieve the scheduling requirement, such as response time and fairness. Synchronization may be required among these decomposed components themselves, like one process requires input from another process to proceed. Hence, a coordinated scheduling is needed to minimize the waiting time and hence to improve systems performance. Process migration has been introduced to improve load sharing, and this leads the processes to run on the most suitable nodes. During the lifetime of a job, the resource status of the system always keeps changing. A good approach should be always a mixed approach, using both space-sharing and time-sharing, with the complementary coscheduling and process migration[17].

In Local scheduling approach[17], each workstation independently schedules its processes, is an attractive time-sharing option for its ease of construction, scalability, fault-tolerance, etc. At the same time, Coordinated scheduling of parallel jobs across the nodes of a multiprocessor (coscheduling) is also indispensable in a distributed system. Without coscheduling, the processes constituting a parallel job might suffer high communication latencies because of processor thrashing. By coordinated scheduling across cooperating processes, each local scheduler is able to make independent decisions that tend to schedule the processes of a parallel application in a coordinated manner across processors, in order to fully exploit the computing resource of a distributed system.

3. Good Scheduler

Considering several factors like support for heterogeneous resources, scalability, coscheduling methods, it is believed that a good scheduler should have few of the following properties

General purpose: System should have been designed to give good performance for Interactive jobs, distributed and parallel applications, as well as non-interactive batch jobs.

Efficiency: System should improve the performance of scheduled jobs as much as possible at low overhead

Fairness: Mainly system should be having the no starvation problems.

Dynamic: Sheduling algorithms should react according to the changes in system load.

Transparency: Process execution should not be affected by the host on which it executes.

4. Local Scheduling

Local scheduling in a distributed system deals about how an individual node schedules the processes assigned to it with the objective to maximize the systems performance. Local scheduling is the same as the scheduling approach on a stand-alone machine. However, in many aspects it differs. The local scheduler needs global information from other workstations to achieve the optimal performance of the entire system in a distributed system. There are many scheduling techniques developed in different models. This paper discuss on two methods mainly the Proportional-Sharing Scheduling approach, and Predictive Scheduling. In Proportional-Sharing Scheduling approach the resource consumption rights of each running process will be proportional to their relative shares allocated to each of process. On the other hand in Predictive Scheduling will be adaptive to the resource distribution as well as CPU load on the distributed system.

4.1 Proportional-Sharing Schedule

Proportional-Share Scheduling has been brought out to effectively solve the problem of starvation under a traditional Priority Scheduling approach. Priority-based schedulers give more processing time to users with many jobs and later leads to unfairness among users. With Proportional-Share Scheduling, the resource consumption rights of a running process is proportional to its relative shares that is allocated. Basically we disucus on one Proportional-Share Scheduling called Stride Scheduling[17].

4.1.1 Stride Scheduling

In Stride Scheduling, resources will be allocated to competing users in proportion to the number of tickets they hold. Each user has a stride, a time interval, that is inversely proportional to their ticket allocation, which determines how frequently it is used. A pass is associated with each user. The user with a minimum pass is scheduled at each interval; a pass is then incremented by the job's stride. Currencies allow clients to distribute tickets in a modular way. Besides these currency, each user has

his own currency. By assigning one currency per user, a proportional-share of resources can be allocated to each user, who in turn can allocate a proportional-share of their resources to execute the processes.

4.1.2 Types of Stride Scheduling

Since the original stride scheduling deals with CPU-bound jobs, in order to handle interactive and I/O intensive workloads, they must be extended to improve the responsive time and I/O throughput. Hence two extensions have been introduced to stride scheduling that give credits to jobs not competing for resources. Here jobs are given incentive to relinquish the processor when not in use and will receive their share of resources over a longer time-interval. Since interactive jobs are scheduled more frequently when they awaken, they can receive better response time. The first type is loan & borrow, and the second extension is system credit. Both approaches are built on exhaustible tickets, having expiration time.

4.1.2.1 Loan & Borrow

In this approach, exhausted tickets are traded among competing users. Other users can borrow inactive tickets while a user temporarily exits the system. The borrowed tickets expire when the user rejoins the system. When the inactive user wakes up, it stops loaning tickets and is paid back in exhaustible tickets by the borrowing users. The lifetime of the exhaustible tickets is equal to the length the original tickets were borrowed. This policy can keep the total number of tickets in the system constant over time. Hence, users can accurately determine the amount of resources they receive. However, it also introduces an excessive amount of computation into the scheduler on every sleep and wake-up event, which we don't expect.

4.1.2.2 System Credit

The second approach is an approximation of loan & borrow. With system credits, clients are given exhaustible tickets from the system when they awaken. The idea behind this policy is that after a client sleeps and awakens, the scheduler calculates the number of exhaustible tickets for the clients to receive its proportional share over some longer interval. The system credit policy is easy to implement and does not add significant overhead to the scheduler on sleep and wakeup events. Figure 2 shows an example of both approaches.

4.2 Predictive Scheduling

Predictive scheduling provides intelligence, adaptivity and proactivity so that the system implementing predictive scheduling can adapt to new architectures and algorithms as well as environmental changes dynamically. Predictive scheduling can learn new algorithms and methods and also architectures which are embedded into the system. They provide some level of guarantees of service. They are designed to anticipate changes to its environment and avoid those changes to become the system performance bottleneck. Predictive scheduling contains three components: H-cell, S-cell and allocator. The H-cell receives information of hardware resource changes such as CPU usage, disk traffic, memory availability, etc., and provides real-time control. S-cell provides long-term control of computational demands like tasks deadline, and its real-time requirements by interrogating the parallel program code. H-cell and S-cell respectively collect information about computational supply and

computational demand, and provide to the allocator the raw data or some intelligent recommendations. The allocator reconciles the recommendations sent by the H-cells and S-cells and schedules jobs according to their deadline, while guaranteeing constraints and enforcing the deadline. In the allocator, the previous inputs, in the form of a vector of performance information are aggregated into sets. Each set corresponds to a scheduling decision. The allocator re-organizes the sets dynamically to keep a limited memory demand by splitting or merging sets. If a new input matches one of the pattern categories, a decision will be made due to the corresponding decision of that pattern set, otherwise a new pattern category is built to associate this new input pattern with corresponding scheduling decision. Most of the scheduling policies are used either when a process blocks or at the end of a time slice, which may reduce the performance because there can be a considerable lapse of time before scheduling is done. Predictive scheduling solves this problem by predicting when a scheduling decision is necessary, or predicting the parameters needed by the scheduling decision when not known in advance. Based on the collected static information like machine type, CPU power, etc along with the dynamic informations like memory free space, CPU load, etc. Predictive scheduling tries to make an educated guess about the future behavior, such as CPU idle time slot, which can be used to make scheduling decisions in advance. Predicting the future performance based on past information is a common strategy, and it can achieve a satisfactory performance in practical work. Predictive scheduling is very effective in performance and reliability enhancement, even with the simplest methods, but at the cost of design complexity and management overhead. Furthermore, it is observed that the more complicated method is used, the more design complexity and management overhead, and the less performance and reliability enhancement.

5. Coscheduling

Coscheduling approach schedules the interacting processes in a job so that all the activities execute simultaneously on distinct workstations. It can produce benefits in both system and individual job efficiency. Without coordinated scheduling, the processor thrashing may lead to high communication latencies and consequently degraded overall performance. With systems connected by high-performance networks that already achieve latencies within tens microseconds, the success of coscheduling becomes a more important factor in deciding the performance. Gang scheduling, Implicit coscheduling and Dynamic Coscheduling are the different flavours of Coscheduling.

5.1 Gang Scheduling

Typical coscheduling approach is Gang scheduling. The approach identifies a job as a gang and its components as gang members. Further, each job is assigned to a class that has the minimum number of workstations that meet the requirement of its gang members based on a one-process-one-workstation policy. The class has a local scheduler, which can have its own scheduling policy. When a job is scheduled, each of its gang members is allocated to a distinct workstation, and thus, the job executes in parallel. When a time-slice finishes, all running gang members are preempted simultaneously, and all processes from a second job are scheduled for the next time-slice. When a job is rescheduled, effort is also made to run the same processes on the same processors.

5.2 Implicit Coscheduling

Implicit coscheduling is a distributed algorithm for time-sharing communicating processes in a cluster of workstations. By observing and reacting to implicit information, local schedulers in the system make independent decisions that dynamically coordinate the scheduling of communicating processes. The principal mechanism involved is two-phase spin-blocking: a process waiting for a message response spins for some amount of time, and then relinquishes the processor if the response does not arrive.

5.3 Dynamic Coscheduling

Dynamic coscheduling makes scheduling decisions driven directly by the message arrivals. When an arriving message is directed to a process that isn't running, a schedule decision is made. The idea derives from the observation that only those communicating processes need to be coscheduled. Therefore, it doesn't require explicit identification to specify the processes need coscheduling. In jobs with fine-grained communication, the sender and receiver are scheduled together and run until one of them blocks or is preempted. Larger collections of communicating processes are coscheduled by transitivity.

6. Conclusion

Several approaches on scheduling and coscheduling are discussed in this paper. Fairness is a very important requirement for the scheduling approaches apart from performance. In Proportional-Sharing Scheduling approach the resource consumption rights of each running process will be proportional to their relative shares allocated to each of process. Stride scheduling fairly allocates resources to a mix of multi-type jobs with improving response time and it suits for a scalable distributed system. Predictive scheduling makes an attempt to schedule dynamically by gathering current systems snapshot and achieving load balancing. In addition to a good scheduling policy, coscheduling is also critical for scheduling processes on distributed systems in order to enhance performance and prevent processor thrashing. Gang scheduling is an approach that plays well on parallel computing systems but suffers with poor fairness. The referred Dynamic Coscheduling and Implicit Coscheduling techniques seem more suitable to such a distributed environment. Combined with a scheduling policy, these two can achieve a fairly good performance on a mixed workload.

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